

First order derivative spectrophotometry for simultaneous determination of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} using 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (DHBINH)

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A first order derivative spectrophotometric method is employed for the determination of molybdenum(VI) and simultaneous determination of molybdenum(VI) and titanium(IV). Molybdenum(VI) gives a golden yellow colour with 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone (DHBINH) in the pH range 1–3. The first derivative spectrum shows maximum amplitude at 490 nm. Beer's law is obeyed the range 0.19 to 6.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Mo^{VI} at 495.5 nm where there is no interference from Ti^{IV} . Molybdenum(VI) and titanium(IV) are determined simultaneously by measuring the derivative amplitudes at 495.5 nm and 580 nm in the concentration ranges 0.2 to 6.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and 0.05 to 2.40 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively, without using simultaneous equations. The method is applied for the analysis of alloy and steel samples for the molybdenum and titanium content with good accuracy.

Hydrazones are found to be potential reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of many metal ions¹. In our earlier studies², the interference of molybdenum in the determination of titanium was observed. A spectrophotometric method was reported for the simultaneous determination of molybdenum and titanium in steels³. The first order derivative spectra of Ti^{IV} -DHBINH and Mo^{VI} -DHBINH showed that both Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} can be simultaneously determined without needing simultaneous equations.

Hence a first derivative spectrophotometric method has been developed for the simultaneous determination of molybdenum(VI) and titanium(IV) using 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone and the results obtained are presented in this paper.

Results and discussion

Molybdenum(VI) reacts with DHBINH forming a golden yellow coloured complex in the pH range 1–3 with two absorption maxima one at 345 nm and another at 445 nm. In first order derivative spectrum, the peak maximum is observed at 490 nm. However, at 495.5 nm there is no interference from titanium(IV) even when present in 20-fold excess. Further, the difference in the derivative amplitude at 490 nm and 495.5 nm is insignificant. Therefore molybdenum is determined at 495.5 nm. Though the yellow coloured solution shows maximum and constant amplitude in the pH range 1 to 3, the studies are carried out at pH 1.5 as the interference from foreign ions is minimum at this pH. A five-fold excess of reagent concentration is necessary to get maximum derivative amplitude. The magnitude of the derivative does not change even after one week.

Determination of Mo^{VI} :

The amplitude of the first order derivative is found to vary linearly with the concentration of Mo^{VI} at 495.5 nm in the range 0.19 to 6.00 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The standard deviation (S), intercept (b) and correlation coefficient (r) of the method are calculated as ± 0.0035 , $+0.009$ and 0.999 , respectively.

Interferences :

The tolerance limits of different cations and anions that interfere in the present method are studied. The amount of foreign ion that causes an error of $\pm 2\%$ in the derivative amplitude is taken as its tolerance limit. It is observed that in presence of 17600 μg of ascorbic acid; Fe^{III} (2000 μg); Cu^{II} (60 μg); V^{V} (30 μg) and W^{VI} (40 μg) are tolerable.

Simultaneous determination of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} :

The first order derivative spectra of Mo^{VI} -DHBINH and Ti^{IV} -DHBINH at pH 1.5 are taken. Molybdenum shows considerable derivative amplitude at 495.5 nm where titanium has zero amplitude (zero cross). At 560 nm, titanium shows a peak. However at 580 nm molybdenum has zero amplitude. Thus Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} are determined simultaneously by measuring the derivative amplitudes at 495.5 and 580 nm, respectively without using simultaneous equations. The method is applied for the determination of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} in synthetic mixtures and the results are presented in Table 1. It can be seen from the results in Table 1 that Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.19 to 6.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of Mo^{VI} and 0.05 to 2.4 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for Ti^{IV} .

Applications :

Molybdenum and titanium present in different alloy and

Table 1. Simultaneous determination of Ti^{IV} and Mo^{VI}

Sample	Amount taken (µg/ml)		Amount found (µg/ml)	
	Ti ^{IV}	Mo ^{VI}	Ti ^{IV}	Mo ^{VI}
1	0.479	0.959	0.470	0.965
2	0.479	1.438	0.475	1.430
3	0.479	1.919	0.481	1.900
4	0.479	2.398	0.484	2.373
5	0.479	2.878	0.475	2.885
6	0.479	3.356	0.476	3.359
7	0.479	0.479	0.488	0.475
8	0.958	0.959	0.960	0.959
9	1.437	0.959	1.430	0.962
10	1.916	0.959	1.906	0.965
11	2.395	0.959	2.405	0.950
12	2.876	0.959	2.866	0.955
BAS-387 alloy ^a	2.95	5.83	2.98	5.80

a : Ni, 41.9; Fe, 36.0; Cr, 12.46; Mo, 5.83; Ti, 2.95, Si, 0.28; Al, 0.24; Co, 0.21; Mn, 0.08; Cu, 0.032; C, 0.03 (%).

steel samples were determined by the present method. The sample solutions were prepared using the procedure reported by Busev *et al.*⁴.

Determination of Mo^{VI} :

The sample solutions were treated with 1 ml of 1 M ascorbic acid to mask Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, V^V and W^{VI}. The amount of molybdenum present in the sample was computed from the pre-determined calibration plot and presented in Table 2.

Simultaneous determination of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} :

Different aliquots of sample solutions were treated as mentioned in procedure (*loc. cit.*). Fe^{III} and Al^{III} present in

Table 2. Analysis of Mo^{VI} in steel and alloy samples

Sample	Amount present (%)	Amount found (%)	Relative error (%)
BCS-219/4 ^a	0.58	0.59	1.7
BAS-307 alloy ^b	5.83	5.80	-0.5
Nickel based high temperature alloy :			
(i) Udimet-500 ^c	4.80	4.85	1.0
(ii) Udimet-700 ^d	5.20	5.15	-1.0

*Average of six determinations.

a : Mn, 0.81; Cr, 0.66; Mo, 0.81; Ni, 2.55; Cu, 0.08; Sn, 0.011; Fe, 95.00.

b : Ni, 41.9; Fe, 36.00; Cr, 12.46; Mo, 5.83; Ti, 2.95; Si, 0.28; Al, 0.24; Co, 0.21; Mn, 0.08; Cu, 0.032; C, 0.03.

c : Cr, 18.0; Co, 18.5; Al, 2.9; Mo, 4.8; C, 0.08; B, 0.006; Zr, 0.05; Ti, 2.9.

d : Cr, 15.0; Co, 18.0; Al, 4.3; Mo, 5.21; C, 0.08; B, 0.0003; Ti, 3.5.

the samples were masked by adding 1 ml of 1 M ascorbic acid and 0.3 ml of 0.1 M citrate respectively. The amounts of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} present in these samples were computed from the pre-determined calibration plots and given in Table 1.

Conclusions :

Several reagents are used as photometric reagents for the determination of Mo^{VI}. Some methods need reducing agents⁵, some suffer from lack of stability and from serious interference by other ions. Majority of the existing procedures are extraction oriented⁶ and some require prior separation of W^{VI}. A recently proposed method using 7,8-dihydroxy-4-methyl coumarin⁷ though sensitive, suffers from the interference of W^{VI}. The present method is rapid, sensitive and highly selective in the presence of ascorbic acid. The procedure for the simultaneous determination of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} is first of its kind which is direct and does not need solving of simultaneous equations. Large amounts of Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mg^{II}, Co^{II}, Hg^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} do not interfere.

Titanium and molybdenum are present in association with each other in many industrially important alloys and steels. Hence their simultaneous determination is very important⁸. The analytical results of the present method are compared with those obtained in some of the recently proposed spectrophotometric methods⁸ and presented in Table 3. Suzuki *et al.*⁹ reported their simultaneous determination by first derivative spectrophotometry using hydrogen peroxide. However they have neither applied the method to any real samples nor studied the interferences of cations other than W^{VI} and V^V. The present method is more sensitive than the above method and has been applied successfully to their analysis in steel samples.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer, UV-160A and Phillips digital pH meter PP 9046 were used for the absorbance and pH measurement respectively.

Reagents :

2,4-Dihydroxy benzaldehyde isonicotinoyl hydrazone :

This was prepared by condensing 2,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde and isonicotinic acid hydrazide in methanol medium using general procedure¹⁰ (m.p. 288–290°). A 0.01 M solution of the reagent in DMF was used in the studies.

Buffer solutions :

They were prepared by mixing 1 M hydrochloric acid and 1 M sodium acetate (pH 1.0 to 3.0) and 0.2 M acetic

Table 3. Comparison with other methods

Reagent	Metal	λ_{\max} (nm)	Aqueous/ extraction	ϵ	Beer's law (mg ml ⁻¹)	Interference	Ref.
Thiocyanate using glutathione as reducing agent	Mo ^{VI}	465	Aqueous	–	1.22–6.40	–	5
<i>N</i> ₁ -Hydroxy- <i>N</i> ₁ , <i>N</i> ₂ -diphenyl benzamidine and thiocyanate	Ti ^{IV}	400	Extraction	2.0×10^4	0.20–0.40	–	6(a)
Thiazolyl blue and thiocyanate	Mo ^V	470	Extraction	5.7×10^4	–	–	6(b)
Bromo pyrogallol red and Zephramine	Mo ^{VI}	634	Extraction	6.0×10^4	0.12–2.00	Fe ^{III} and Cr were removed as hydroxides	6(c)
<i>N</i> ₁ -(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl)- <i>N</i> ₁ -hydroxy- <i>N</i> ₂ -(<i>o</i> -methylphenyl)benzamidine hydrochloride and thiocyanate	Mo ^V	470	Extraction	3.77×10^3	3.00–22.00	–	6(d)
3-Hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4- <i>H</i> -chromen-4-one	Mo ^{VI}	411	Extraction	5.61×10^4	0–2.30	Sn ^{II} , Ce ^{IV} citrate, oxalate, EDTA and H ₂ O ₂ interfere	6(e)
7,8-Dihydroxy-4-methyl coumarin	Mo ^{VI}	400	Aqueous	1.32×10^5	0.60	Zr ^{IV} and W ^{VI} interfere	7
6-(4-Nitrophenyl azo)-3,4,5-tri-hydroxy benzoic acid	Ti ^{IV}	495	Aqueous	3.48×10^4	0.04–1.00	–	8(a)

acid and 0.2 *M* sodium acetate (pH 3.5 to 7.0) in various proportions. The pH of these solutions was adjusted to their appropriate values using pH meter.

Molybdenum(VI) and titanium(IV) solution :

0.01 *M* solutions of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} were prepared by dissolving requisite amounts of analytical grade Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O and K₂TiO(C₂O₄)₂·2H₂O in distilled water and standardized. Lower concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Procedure :

Determination of Mo^{VI} :

To each of a set of different 10 ml volumetric flask, 5 ml of buffer solution (pH 1.5) and 0.5 ml of DHBINH (1×10^{-2} *M*) were added. Various amounts of Mo^{VI} were added to these flasks and made up to the mark with distilled water. First order derivative spectra of these solutions were recorded with scan speed of nearly 2400 nm min⁻¹. With 9 degree of freedom in the wavelength range 800 to 400 nm. The derivative peak heights were measured by peak-zero method at 495.5 nm. The peak height was plotted against the amount and incorporated in the straight line equation $y = mx + b$; where x is concentration of metal solution, y is measured absorbance; m and b are constants which are the slope and intercept of the straight line respectively. The values of m and b for the present method were calculated

from the experimental data and substituted in the above equation to get $y = 0.052x + 0.005$ which gives the best straight line.

Simultaneous determination of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} :

1.3 ml DHBINH (1×10^{-2} *M*) and 5 ml buffer solution (pH 1.5) taken in each of a set of different 10 ml volumetric flasks, various known aliquots of Mo^{VI} and Ti^{IV} were added. A slight turbidity was developed in the reaction mixture. This was dissolved and clear solution was obtained by adding 1 ml of DMF and 1 ml of *n*-butanol. The contents were made up to the mark with distilled water and the first order derivative spectra for these solutions were recorded against the reagent blank in the wavelength region 800–400 nm. The peak heights were measured at 495.5 nm for Mo^{VI} and at 580 nm for Ti^{IV}. Calibration plots were drawn for the experimental data which follow the straight line equations and were found to be $y = 0.052x + 0.005$ for Mo^{VI} and $y = 0.076x + 0.005$ for Ti^{IV}.

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